

HAO1 inhibitor development: Structural studies with first round of follow-up compounds from TEP fragment screen - deposition 1 of 3

Introduction: The overarching aim of my project is to start development of small molecule inhibitors of HAO1 (hydroxy-acid oxidase 1/ glycolate oxidase) as a treatment for primary hyperoxaluria, a rare inborn error of metabolism in which the pathogenic driver is accumulation of glyoxylate, the product of HAO1. A more in depth introduction is provided on my Open Lab Notebook blog here: <https://openlabnotebooks.org/project-overview-inhibition-of-hao1-to-treat-primary-hyperoxaluria-type-1/>

Previous work: We performed a fragment screen of HAO1 by x-ray crystallography and confirmed binding of four fragment hits in three biologically relevant sites – active site, gating loop and oligomeric interface – by SPR. Fluorescence-based activity assay (Amplex Red) showed inhibition of HAO1 by two fragments that bound to the active site and one fragment that bound to the gating loop. This data is available as part of an SGC Target Enabling Package (TEP) on Zenodo here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1342618>. We ordered 40 compounds based on the active site fragment scaffolds and 75 compounds based on the gating loop fragment scaffold and synthesised 15 compounds based on the oligomeric interface fragment scaffold. These compounds were tested for hHAO1 inhibition in an established fluorescence-based activity assay with several showing improved inhibition. Details can be found on Zenodo here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1477079> and here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2341173>.

Aim of this work: To obtain crystal structures with follow-up compounds to guide structure-based drug design. Further details can be found in my Open Lab Notebook blog post here: <https://openlabnotebooks.org/results-from-soaking-follow-up-compounds-into-preformed-hao1-crystals/>

Materials and Methods

Construct details:

Vector: pNIC28-Bsa4; Entry Clone Accession: NM_017545; Cell line: BL21 (DE3)-R3/Rosetta; Tags and additions: N-terminal, TEV protease cleavable hexahistidine tag; Construct protein sequence:

Mhhhhhhsgvdlgtenlyfq*sMLPRLICINDYEQHAKSVLPKSIYDYRSGANDEETLADNIAAFSRWKLYPRMLRNVAETDLSTSVLGQ RVSMPICVGATAMQRMAHVDGELATVRACQSLGTGMMLSSWATSSIEEVAEAGPEALRWLQLYIKDREVTKKLVRQAEEKMGYKAI FVTVDTPYLGNRLLDDVRNRFKLPQRLMKNFETSTLSFSPEENFGDDSGLAAYVAKAIDPSISWEDIKWLRRLTSLPIVAKGILRGDDAR EAVKHGLNGILVSNHGARQLDGVDPATIDVLPEIVEAVEGKVEVFLDGGVRKGTDLKALALGAKAVFVGRPIVWGLAFQGEKGVQDV LEILKEEFRLAMALSGCQNVKVIDKTLVRKNPLAVSKI(Underlined sequence contains vector encoded His-tag and TEV protease cleavage site*)

Protein expression:

An overnight culture (20 mL LB) was used to inoculate 2L auto-induction TB containing 50 µg/ml each of kanamycin and chloramphenicol. Cells were cultured at 37°C for 6 hours followed by 48 h incubation at 18°C.

Purification buffers:

Extraction Buffer: 500 mM NaCl, 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 20 mM imidazole, 0.5 mM TCEP, 5% glycerol, 1:1000 of Merck Protease Cocktail II, 0.5 mg/mL lysozyme and 0.2 µg/mL benzonase; Binding Buffer: 500 mM NaCl, 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 20 mM imidazole, 0.5 mM TCEP, 5% glycerol; Washing Buffer: 500 mM NaCl, 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 40 mM imidazole, 0.5 mM TCEP, 5% glycerol; Elution Buffer: 500 mM NaCl, 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 250 mM imidazole, 0.5 mM TCEP, 5% glycerol; GF buffer: 500 mM NaCl, 50 mM HEPES pH 7.5, 0.5 mM TCEP, 5% glycerol.

Protein purification:

Cell pellet from 2 L of culture was re-suspended in 150 mL Extraction Buffer, lysed by sonication for 15 minutes, and centrifuged at 37000 x g for 1 hour at 4°C. The clarified cell extract was incubated with 5 mL of Ni-NTA resin pre-equilibrated with Binding Buffer before applying to 1.5 x 10 cm column by gravity flow. The column was washed with 10 column volumes of Binding Buffer, 10 column volumes of Wash Buffer, and eluted with 5 x 5 mL Elution Buffer. Fractions containing hHAO1 were loaded onto gel filtration column (Superdex 200 Hiload 16/60) pre-equilibrated with GF buffer. Fractions containing hHAO1 were pooled and protein purity confirmed by SDS-PAGE. Protein identity was confirmed by intact mass spectrometry and tryptic digest MS/MS of the gel band.

Crystallisation for soaking experiments:

Crystals were grown by vapour diffusion at 4°C in sitting drops of 15 mg/mL protein equilibrated against well solution containing 25-35% PEG1000, sodium malonate-imidazole-boric acid pH 8.0.

Co-crystallisation with compounds:

Purified hHAO1 (15 mg/ml) was preincubated with 10-fold excess of compound (3.5 mM final concentration) for 30 minutes on ice before setting up crystal trials. For each compound, one plate of the LFS6 commercial sparse matrix screen was set up with 150 nL sitting drops at 4°C.

Soaking experiments:

For both sets of crystals, 37.5 nL of each compound (final concentration of 20 mM, 20% DMSO) was added to a crystallization drop using an ECHO acoustic liquid handler dispenser at the Diamond light source XChem facility. Crystals were soaked for two hours before being harvested using XChem SHIFTER technology, cryo-cooled in liquid nitrogen, and data sets collected at the beamline I04-1 in "automated unattended" mode. The XChemXplorer pipeline was used for structure solution with parallel molecular replacement using DIMPLE (template 6GMB), followed by map averaging and statistical modelling to identify weak electron densities generated from low occupancy fragments using Pandda software.

Results – part 1

Protein purification and crystallisation: 1L AI-TB culture yielded 40 mg of hHAO1 protein of high purity. Standard crystallisation in an optimised screen (25-30% PEG1000, 0.1 M MIB buffer, pH 7.5-8.0) yielded large, diamond-shaped, yellow HAO1 crystals, suitable for compound soaking, in 4-7 days. Co-crystal trials had varying success with several crystals appearing visually poorer (rounded edges and smaller in size) or of different crystal forms (thin plates, cubes).

Data collection outcomes: 90% of all soaked crystals (not co-crystals) yielded useable DIMPLE models of < 2.5 Å resolution. Of the remaining 10%, some crystals did not survive soaking resulting in either a failure to mount crystal (2%); a failure to collect data (7%) or reduced resolution (2%). The soaked co-crystals were less robust, primarily due to their smaller size/difficulty in mounting – 68% yielded datasets at < 2.5 Å.

Outcome of soaking into preformed crystals: Inspection of the collected datasets showed surprisingly few binding events. Four datasets of interest have been analysed so far: two at the active site, one at the gating loop and one at the oligomeric interface. Compound names, structures and links to the related maps/models are shown in the table below. Discussion of the structures can be found on the related Open Lab Notebook blog post here:

<https://openlabnotebooks.org/results-from-soaking-follow-up-compounds-into-preformed-hao1-crystals/>

Compound ID	Active site "FUP1A"	Active site "FUP2A"	Loop site "FUP5A"	Interface site "FUP6A"
Compound structure				
IUPAC name	5-bromo-N-methyl-1H-indazole-3-carboxamide	6-amino-1-benzyl-5-(methylamino) pyrimidine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione	(2-((4H-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)thio)-1-(4-(3-chlorophenyl)piperazin-1-yl)ethan-1-one	1-(5-chloropyrimidin-4-yl)-4-(pyridin-2-yl)piperazine
Link to data files				
% inhibition at 1 mM	26%	37%	12%	78% (22% at 0.75 mM)